

Stability Constants of Transition Metal Complexes of 2-Hydroxy-1-Naphthalidene-p-Methylaniline

M. S. MAYADEO

Department of Chemistry, Ramnarain Ruia College Bombay-400 019

Manuscript received 28 September 1974 ; revised 4 March 1975 ; accepted 17 March 1975

The proton dissociation constant of the ligand and the stability constants of the complexes of Cu(II), Ni(II), Zn(II), Co(II), Cd(II) and Mg(II) with 2-hydroxy-1-naphthalidene-p-methylaniline have been determined potentiometrically at $30^\circ \pm 0.1^\circ$ and at ionic strength 0.1M in 75:25 (v/v) dioxan-water medium. Log K_1 and log K_2 values have been determined. The stabilities of the chelates follow the order $Cu > Ni > Zn > Co > Cd > Mg$.

IN the present communication are reported the successive stability constants of the complexes of 2 hydroxy-1-naphthalidene-p methylaniline with various bivalent metal ions which have been determined potentiometrically following the Calvin-Bjerrum pH titration technique as adopted by Irving and Rossotti¹.

Experimental

The Corning Model 12, a precision research pH meter with a wide range glass electrode and a Calomel reference electrode was used for pH measurements. The meter has an arrangement for normal and expanded scale. The smallest scale division on the expanded scale is 0.005 pH unit.

The ligand 2-hydroxy-1-naphthalidene-p-methylaniline was synthesised and crystallised to get an analytically pure sample (m. p. $132^\circ-133^\circ$)².

The medium of titration was dioxan-water mixture containing 75% (v/v) of dioxan. The dioxan used for the experiments was purified by the method described by Vogel.³ Distilled water, redistilled over alkaline potassium permanganate and made free from carbon dioxide by boiling, was used throughout the investigation. Sodium perchlorate was added to maintain a constant ionic strength (0.1M). The titrations were carried out in an inert atmosphere by bubbling the nitrogen gas through the solutions. All the metal perchlorate solutions were standardised complexometrically⁴ by E. D. T. A. titrations. All measurements were made at $30^\circ \pm 0.1^\circ$.

The following solutions were titrated potentiometrically against standard carbonate free sodium hydroxide (1.092M) solution, keeping the total volume 40 ml.

(i) 5 ml of (0.16M) $HClO_4$ + 5 ml of (0.64M) $NaClO_4$ + 30 ml of dioxan.

(ii) 5 ml of (0.16M) $HClO_4$ + 5 ml of (0.64M) $NaClO_4$ + requisite amount of the reagent accurately weighed to give 0.01M reagent concentration in the final solution + 30 ml of dioxan.

(iii) 5 ml of (0.64M) $NaClO_4$ + 5 ml of (0.024M) metal salt solution in (0.16M) $HClO_4$ + requisite amount of the reagent accurately weighed to give 0.01M reagent concentration in the final solution in the case of Cu^{+2} , Ni^{+2} , Co^{+2} , Zn^{+2} , Cd^{+2} and 0.05M reagent concentration in the case of Mg^{+2} + 30 ml of dioxan.

The method of Irving and Rossotti¹ was applied to find out the values of \bar{n} and pL.

Results and Discussion

In the ligand, it is the chelated phenolic 'OH' group which takes part in the complex formation and the proton is replaced from it by metal ions during the formation of metal chelates. Since only one proton per ligand molecule is liberated during complexation, 'y', the number of dissociable protons attached per ligand molecule is equal to one.

From the titration curves using the solutions (i) and (ii), \bar{n}_A values at various 'B' values (pH meter readings) were calculated, and the curve between 'B' and the corresponding \bar{n}_A values was plotted (Fig. 1). The formation curve extends over a range $0.80 < \bar{n}_A < 1.8$ and is wavelike. This indicates the formation of the species HL and H_2^+L , i. e. the protonated nitrogen and the phenolic hydrogen are completely dissociable in steps. The value of pK_2^H only could be evaluated from half integral point at $\bar{n}_A = 1.5$. The value of pK_1^H could not be found by half integral and graphical methods. It was however determined by least square method.

Fig. 1—2-Hydroxy-1 Naphthalidene-p-Methylaniline Formation Curve.

A plot of $\log \left[\frac{2 - \bar{n}_A}{1 - \bar{n}_A} \right]$ against 'B' was also drawn. (Fig. 2). From this curve the value of practical pK_2^H was evaluated. The two values agree fairly well.

Fig. 2—2-Hydroxy-1-Naphthalidene-p-Methylaniline

From the titration curves of the solutions (ii) and (iii) \bar{n} and pL values were calculated. The \bar{n} values were plotted against the corresponding pL values to get the formation curves of the metal complexion equilibria. (Fig. 3). From these formation curves the values of stability constants $\log K_1$ and $\log K_2$ were determined

Fig. 3—Metal-Ligand Systems of 2-Hydroxy-1-Naphthalidene-p-Methylaniline Formation Curves.

which correspond to the pL values at $\bar{n} = 0.5$ and 1.5 respectively. In addition, the least square method was also applied to calculate $\log K_1$ and $\log K_2$ in the case of Cu, Ni and Co. The most representative values are recorded in the Table 1.

TABLE 1—STEPWISE STABILITY CONSTANTS OF VARIOUS COMPLEXES^(a)

t=30°	H ⁺	Cu ⁺²	Ni ⁺²	Co ⁺²	Zn ⁺²	Cd ⁺²	Mg ⁺²
log K ₁	9.83	9.39	5.70	5.20	5.55	4.36	3.53
log K ₂	3.08	7.86	4.67	4.79	—	—	—

(a) H⁺, K₁ and K₂ correspond to the species LH and LH₂ respectively, while for the metal ions K₁ and K₂ correspond to the species ML and ML₂ respectively.

The order of stability of bivalent metal chelates was Cu⁺² > Ni⁺² > Zn⁺² > Co⁺² > Cd⁺² > Mg⁺².

The order in the case of Zn⁺² complex is reversed with respect to Co⁺², as compared to that observed by Maley and Mellor⁵.

Fig. 4—Formation Constants and Fundamental Properties of 2-Hydroxy-1-Naphthalidene-p-Methylaniline Complexes.

A parallelism between log K and second ionisation potential (I. P.) is also observed in the present case as has been suggested by Irving and Williams⁶. This is indicated graphically in Fig. 4, obtained by plotting the formation constants (stability constants) and the ionisation potentials as a function of the atomic number.

Acknowledgement

The author wishes to record his sincere thanks to Dr. D. G. Vartak of B.A.R.C., Bombay for his valuable suggestions.

References

1. H. M. IRVING and H. S. ROSSOTTI., *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1954, 2904.
2. *Beilstein*, 12, 916.
3. A. I. VOGEL., 'A Test Book of Practical Organic Chemistry', III Edition, Longmans, p. 177.
4. G. SCHWARZENBACH., 'Complexometric Titrations', Methuen and Co. Ltd., London, 1956, p. 60.
5. L. E. MALEY and D. P. MELLOR., *Nature*, 1947, 159, 370.
6. H. IRVING and R. J. P. WILLIAMS., *Nature*, 1948, 162, 746; *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1953, 3192.